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UBIQUITOUS URBAN GAME

BETWEEN MEANING PRODUCTION AND THE PRODUCTION OF PRESENCE

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ABSTRACT

During translation from the realm of reality into that of the mind, substantial reality is distorted, having as result a schematized environmental image, constructed from the alteration of presence phenomena into meaning.

By attaching meaning to all their experiences, people build up a personalized system of interpretation of the world, which, in return, produces tension, whenever interacting with another individually- or culturally- defined system or with the substantial reality.

By means of a ubiquitous urban game, this paper aims to investigate the effects of locative and media technologies on the relation between presence and meaning, and from here, on the emerging tension. Subsequently, it will explore the tactics people develop in order to tackle tension and to attain an enhanced coping with their living environment.

Keywords: ubiquitous game, presence, meaning.

INTRODUCTION

Acting in the familiar environment most of the times does not entail present-aware participation of the individual. Although any type of interaction with the environment implies a physical relation between the body and the space, the effect of this interaction does not necessarily generate conscious sensory perception; it rather produces meaningful images to be mentally processed further into a set of impressions.

The sum of these images comprise what Lynch (1960) called "the environmental image" - a comprehensive picture of the external physical world held by an individual. This mental image is the result of a two-

way process of perceiving and conceiving the environment.

A holistic appraisal of the environmental image investigates the cognitive, ecologic and phenomenological features that mediate the process of acquisition of environmental knowledge. This threefold integration explains how people construct their mental images from embodied experiences and reveals a tension that emerges between present and meaningful experiences, between sensory observation and interpretation. Hans Ulrich Gumbrecht (2004) extensively tackles this tension in his referential book, "Production of Presence - What Meaning Cannot Convey"; he observes an ever increasing separation from the "things of the world", separation which is facilitated and assisted by our dominantly interpretative approach, which pervades all our daily relations with the world. Presence, understood by Gumbrecht as the sense of actually being "in a spatial relationship to the world and its objects" (Gumbrecht, 2004, p. xiii), is lacking almost completely when people are interacting with the environment. People are not aware of their perceptions, since they live extensively "in their heads" (Sofronie & Devisch, 2010), where meaning is continually negotiated in relation to a culturally- and subjectively-defined reference frame.

Presence and meaning, thus, "always appear together and always in tension" (Gumbrecht, 2004, p.105). This tension has its root in the Cartesian model introduced by Descartes, according to which, there is a clear dichotomy between the activity of the mind and that of the body, between the person and the environment, between reason and emotion. In our Cartesian daily life, the dimension of meaning is dominant, producing an ever-growing distance between us and the world, up to the point of an absolute loss of contact with our bodies and with the

substantial reality around them. This led to a present societal situation in which present moments have so completely vanished that, Gumbrecht observes, they are now coming back in the form of “an intense desire for presence, reinforced or even triggered by many of our contemporary communication media” (Gumbrecht, 2004, p.20). This may come as a paradox, since these media technologies were initially meant to fulfill the so-called Cartesian dream- the dream of omnipresence, by which lived experiences can be grasped independently of the locations that bodies occupy in space (Gumbrecht, 2004).

By means of designing and testing a ubiquitous urban game which relies on locative and media technologies, the purpose of this paper is to investigate what are the effects of such technologies on the relation between presence and meaning and their potential impact on the urban planning practice.

While following Gumbrecht and the meaning- and presence-cultures he introduces, the game deals with two types of knowledge: *interpretative knowledge*- subjectively produced by the residents through daily experiences and by the spatial experts through training; and *revealed knowledge* - enhanced in moments of sheer present observation of the environment.

As a participatory tool that in urban design, this game facilitates an exchange of knowledge between the designers and the users of space, as essential for the design of spatial proposals that may better suit the specific ways of living of communities. Along this line, the game is initially conceived as an innovative ethnographic tool, which observes people’s daily behavior, by means of locative technologies. Analysis of people’s behavior in space brings insight into the tactics they employ when coping with their environment. In the second step, the game enables a process of sharing this knowledge between the residents and the spatial expert. In parallel with this distribution of interpretative knowledge, the game aims to trigger, by means of location-based annotations and assignments, production of knowledge revealed through present perception of the things of the world, introducing thus the human body as an active player in the game.

In this way, and in line with Gumbrecht’s discourse, the game acknowledges the importance of both the mind and the body in the holistic person-environment system. It actually facilitates an exchange of meaningful knowledge produced by all actors involved in the urban planning practice, while it promotes a sensory re-connection with the environment, as a primary incentive for cultivating that compound feeling of belonging to a place (Norberg Schulz, 1996).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

ENVIRONMENTAL IMAGE

The theoretical framework of the environmental image assesses it as a complex synthesis between cognitive, sensory, and phenomenological traits (Sofronie&Devisch, 2010). While cognitivism embraces the Cartesian model as a foundation for its theories, the ecologic and phenomenological paradigms are situated in opposition to this dualism, considering the person-in-the-environment as the unitary system under evaluation. Despite their conflicting nature, the integration of these three paradigms engenders a holistic appraisal of the way people use, perceive and conceive their environment.

By means of cognitive organizing principles, which follow similar patterns from childhood (Piaget, 1956) till adulthood (Siegel& White, 1975), people merge together pieces of information into an encompassing personalized perspective. Information may come either directly from present observation- through sensory perception of the environment-, or from interpretation of imagined sources- verbal descriptions, remembered experiences, memories of maps, pictures, etc. (Tversky, 2003). A rooted environmental experience provides with a combination of these two modalities acquired through presence and meaning, while unrooted experiences draw heavily on interpretation alone. Either ways, a “highly filtered set of impressions” (Gould et al., 1974, p.29) is selected to enter the pervasive internal information processing. The result is a simplified version of reality (Walmsley, 1988) - in cognitive sciences also known as mental map (Gould et al., 1974), or cognitive map (Tolman, 1948)-, and, within this research, referred to as the

“environmental image” (Lynch, 1960; Appleyard, 1969), since it entails cognition, but also affect, meaning and valuation.

People constantly imbue all external information with emotional and/or functional meanings, creating their own encoding strategies to facilitate memory. In this way, information entering the environmental image is hierarchically structured around personal reference points, also known as anchor points (Golledge, 1978). This internal organization of information around a highly subjectively- defined frame or perspective (Tversky, 2003) illustrates how people are producing their system of interpreting the world in light of own needs, goals, values, and concepts- what Metzinger (2009) referred to as the “ego-tunnel”. These systems-of-interpretation assist people to act effectively in space, and eventually determine all their future actions. For groups of people having some particular things in common (e.g. same living area, same age, same ethnic, social, cultural or educational background) their individual interpretations may partially overlap, generating shared systems of interpretation. Shared systems of interpretation of people living in the same geographical area for a long period of time provide the common ground of local knowledge - the so-called “genius loci” knowledge, the guardian spirit of a place (Norberg-Schulz, 1979).

Acknowledging the embodied cognition discourse, environmental image assessment illustrates how cognition is grounded in “the physical features, innate abilities, practical activity, and environment of thinking agents” (Anderson, 2003, p.126). Human cognition being deeply rooted in sensorimotor processes, the mind must always be considered in the context of its relationship to a physical body that interacts with the world. (Wilson, 2002, p.625) This standpoint should legitimate the idea that, even though impossible to bring in one well-balanced phenomenal structure (Gumbrecht, 2004), meaning and presence are mutually dependent, since the production of one always occurs in detriment of the other.

Emergence of meaning, obviously, diminishes the moments of presence, as interpretation always asks for attention to be distributed away from the substantial, physical reality- conveyed by the body in the environment-, towards conceptual analysis. At

the same time, the starting point of any lived experience lies in a -usually undetected and long-forgotten- presence moment, which has initially sheltered the whole experience. Having such an ephemeral lifespan within our dominant meaning culture, presence phenomena become “presence effects”, as they are “necessarily surrounded by, wrapped into, and perhaps even mediated by clouds and cushions of meaning” (Gumbrecht, 2004, p.1).

THE ENVIRONMENT - AN ARENA FOR ACTION

As Lynch (1960) observed, people largely use their environmental image to interpret information and to guide their actions. Therefore it seems challenging to investigate the relation between presence and meaning- and the tension it produces-, in the course of action, given that action represents the central mode of environmental experience.

Although Gumbrecht considers that action does not belong to a presence culture repertoire, this paper ventures the assumption that action must hold both a presence and a meaning component. The environment is frequently considered an “arena for action” (Ittelson, 1978, p. 204), which implies that action is always situated in a physical circumstance - the body in space-, allowing us to perceive things as they are. Subsequently, this assumes our own impression of how we would like things to be, and from here, behaving towards this purpose. The friction that arises between the desire to be somewhere and actually being there creates an effect of distance, which, Gumbrecht notices, is the instigator of the permanent tension between meaning and presence. Action, obviously, accentuates this tension.

MEANING, PRESENCE AND TENSION

While following the “meaning” component of action, Ittelson (1978, p.201) states that “experience of the environment is never passive”, since people always act within their specific goals. Their patterns of exploration, developed from interpretation, affect the actions they undertake, in a continuous loop of cause and effect. Thus, by attaching meaning, people constantly create the situation within which they have their experience (Ittelson, 1978). Within this frame, this is apparently the moment when tension occurs. Tension will never appear in

moments of sheer presence, but it actually emerges as a result of meaning attachment, as defense of one's perspective. Thus tension is produced from the resistance offered by the individual system of interpretation to other systems of interpretation (individually- or culturally-defined) or even to the present moment observation. More precisely, the individual system of interpretation may display tension when interacting with another individual system of interpretation - as it is the process of agreeing with or adopting someone else's perspective, during a conversation. But also individual systems of interpretation constantly display tension while interacting with the system of interpretation of the society- the system of regulations and ethical, moral, religious, aesthetic, etc. values defined by a particular culture. Whether manifested consciously or not, this tension is reflected back in people's actions, which, Ittelson (1978) observes, are meant to change the person-environment system, with the intention of changing or maintaining the nature of the ongoing environmental experience. Despite the produced tension, individuals tend to perceive this transformation "as their main vocation" (Gumbrecht, 2004, p.82), driven by their interpretation of the world.

Under these circumstances, present moments automatically pass unobservable, since the main actor on the stage of our daily experiences is the 'mental noise' produced by the continuous process of interpretation. Whenever available, however, present moments have an immediate impact on the human body. Hence presence is directly related to sensory perception, which the ecological tradition-introduced by Gibson (1979)-, asserts as the most straightforward way to elicit information embedded in the environment. In line with the Gibsonian approach, action is regarded as a critical facet of sensory perception, and from here also the name "perception-in-action" (Gibson, 1979).

Gumbrecht, however, proposes a somehow different approach of relating to the environment: by observing, from a quiet place in the mind, what is happening unconcealed before us, as an ongoing double movement of unconcealment and withdrawal from acting. This presupposes the capacity of letting things be - defined by Heidegger (1992) as

"Gelassenheit", that capacity to abandon any conceptual manipulation or interpretation of the world. In this way, presence arises as redemption from the permanent obligation to move and to change (Gumbrecht, 2004, p.138), to follow the dynamic of society. While moving away from this never-ending cycle of action and interpretation, the desire of re-connecting with what Tversky (2003) calls "the space of the body" and "the space around the body" may finally arise through calm observation. Only then, this tension usually produced through action can be completely eliminated. Although presence can be ideally achieved through quiet observation, it can also be observable in every single act that we make, by maintaining a present-awareness in regard to our bodies and the surroundings. The more frequent our moments of present awareness, the more rooted our actions become. These actions arise from knowledge revealed through observance of presence moments, instead of being produced in an act of world-interpretation (Gumbrecht, 2004). These presence moments have the ability to make people see things differently from ordinary, from a standpoint where all tensions are eliminated because all cultural and personal dimensions are absent, a standpoint rooted in the substantial reality where the performance occurs.

Tension -sometimes referred to as frustration (Jenkins, 2006), or friction (Huygbrecht, 2011)-, has been defined as "the 'rubbing of' people on each other (...) when people, who hold different backgrounds, understandings and experiences, meet on the bus or in the street and exchange opinions, stories or maybe just gestures and glances" (Jensen & Lenskiold, 2004). These authors consider tension a positive feature, playing a creative role in participatory processes, while producing "a repository of energy that in turn will alter and drive social and cultural phenomena forward in often unpredictable ways" (Jensen & Lenskjold, 2004). The theoretical framework introduced by this paper illustrates tension as an inner resistance to all external stimuli which do not identify with one's system-of-interpreting the world. Nevertheless, a life without meaning is considered "literally dead to the world" (Arendt, H., 1998, p. 176), since functioning in the society always implies

identification with a self- and culturally -defined frame of meanings. From here, the aim is to make explicit tensions in human existence and to understand how people deal with such tensions by developing individual tactics. The method promoted by the game is two-fold. First, a re-awakening of the desire for presence is proposed as the only tension-free state of existence. And second, the game aims to facilitate a smoother tuning to the various (individual or cultural) systems of interpretation with which people interact on a daily basis. To do so, it follows a strategy based on observation, rather than interpretation: identification of existence of tension, in the first place, and then accepting it, while understanding its cause.

GAME CONCEPT

In line with the theoretical framework, the game concept embraces a double strategy, related to the previously revised concepts, of presence and meaning. As such, the game deals with two types of knowledge: knowledge produced through interpretation, and knowledge revealed through presence observation. Interpretation and observation of the environment alternate during the game, in an attempt to validate meaning, through conversations, and to enhance presence by means of location-based assignments.

As a participation tool in urban design, the game facilitates an exchange of knowledge between the residents and the spatial experts. Such knowledge is produced through interpretation of the environment, coming from everyday experiences or from specialized training. To achieve its purpose, the game employs Gordon Pask's Conversation Theory (Pask, 1976) as a methodology to assist and validate learning, by means of conversations. Such conversations occur between a teacher and a learner. Traditionally, the lines of knowledge distribution coincide with the lines of power relations (Gumbrecht, 2004), establishing spatial experts as teachers, and inhabitants as learners. However, the game proposes an alternative solution- a switch of the classical roles. As such, residents are regarded to be the teachers, having the game as a facilitator to make explicit their behavior and, from here, their tactics, to themselves and, eventually, to the spatial expert, who is learning about the way

they cope with the place through these conversations.

The purpose of these conversations is to elicit, construct and validate knowledge about a subject matter. This process entails two types of knowledge: knowing how - practical knowledge- and knowing why- pure conceptual knowledge, both being considered by Pask as complementary aspects of learning. While both these types of knowledge are interpretative- since they emerged from the meaning people attached to them-, it is noticeable that practical knowledge emerged from a present moment, being directly produced through physical actions in the environment. For this reason, this practical knowledge will be tested by means of locative technologies, requiring attainment of location-based tasks.

The game is conceived of two sessions, as follows. In STEP I, participants- playing the role of teachers- provide practical and conceptual knowledge about the way they use and experience their living environment. Practical knowledge- knowledge how- is obtained by mapping their behavior, - through means of a location-based application (Everytrail) running on their smart phones. During one-week period, participants' daily activity space will be monitored in a non-intrusive manner by means of GPS-recordings of their routes through the city. Along these routes, they are asked to make annotations- photos, videos or notes - regarding the environment around them, observing scenes that have some kind of emotional or sensory impact on them. Employing locative technology (GPS), the game is able to track present and meaning effects of people's context-related experiences. Recordings of sensory perceptions or of instant facts in such a direct manner present a clear advantage compared to retrospection - where remembrance of facts, situations or sensations can be somehow distorted or contaminated. From here, we stress the necessity of recording perception in action, encouraging exploration in real-world situations.

These annotations are expected to be nothing but simple, superficial statements. A series of individual open-ended interviews are conducted next, during which participants are asked to detail and to reflect upon the deeper meaning of their experiences. Their previously mapped actions, together with their

reflections will be further analyzed through in-depth thematic analysis, in order to discover the tactics people apply when using their surroundings. In this way, and in line with the non-manipulative approach of the game, conceptual knowledge about the way people use their environment will be produced through researcher's observation and interpretation of the facts, rather than imposed by expert-defined categories.

In STEP II, the knowledge collected in the first step is taught to the learner, who is the spatial expert. To confirm his understanding, the learner must bring, in return, practical and conceptual explanations.

Practical demonstrations call for a future spatial proposal that shows consideration for the individual tactics; they entail completion of location-based challenges. These challenges promote presence observation, since they entail players' direct confrontation with the familiar environment, which must be explored from a new perspective. Tension is avoided this way, since the player is not required to step out beyond the familiar, known area in the city - his "comfort zone". This is an important feature promoted by the game, which takes into consideration the role of familiarity as a source of comfort (Herzog, Kaplan & Kaplan, 1976).

Furthermore, theoretical explanations imply that the learner is able to reproduce and build the topic from other concepts already existing in his mental structure. When teachers and learners are coming from different backgrounds- as it is usually the case with inhabitants and spatial experts- a certain tension is produced in the process of exchanging information, since their systems of interpreting the world differ to a great extent. In this respect, the game facilitates a smoother tuning between the two universes of discourse.

In the end, learner's capacity to produce both practical and theoretical explanations validate the critical method of learning employed by the Conversation theory, the "teach back", which entails that one person is able to teach another what he has learned.

By means of this exchange of knowledge, designers and users may eventually adopt each others' perspective. Future designs conceived by the spatial expert will use genius loci knowledge as guiding principles, in addition to the already existing

knowledge received through specialized training. Accordingly, participants will, most likely, tackle future spatial interventions without skepticism or disbelief, since these are designed in line with their own tactics of coping with the city. Following this non-intrusive approach, the game performs as an innovative design tool for raising issues and asking questions, while not imposing answers. Participants are appropriating these future spatial proposals into their lives without experiencing tension, through their own tactics and interpretation.

Within this concept, the game is situated outside the classical theories of play (Huizinga, 1955), which frame play within the "magic circle", around well-defined boundaries of time and space according to fixed rules. In contrast to this approach, our ubiquitous urban game connects play with everyday aspects of life, blurring the boundaries between play and daily life and by transforming the familiar environment into a play-space that awaits rediscovery. Within this frame, ambiguity is considered a resource for design (Gaver et al., 2003), being employed as a valuable tool for non-manipulative research. Ambiguity has the potential to engage participants with issues without constraining them how to respond, and simultaneously, it conveys the expert's perspective, while enabling participants to find their own interpretations, derived from their different socio-cultural backgrounds (Gaver et al., 2003). In this way, the rules are minimally-defined, not as ultimate goals but as hints for navigation (de Souza e Silva et al., 2009).

TESTING

The concept of this ubiquitous urban game, as described above, has been tested in responsive experimental trials. Through these trials, technological enhancements are sorted out, while the players' performances inform the research process itself. This "learning by doing" approach establishes as a feedback loop in which the game performs not as an end product, but rather as a progressive one.

Experiments have been done typically on groups of five participants, selected from a diverse range of age. Within each group, a balanced ratio (2:3) between architecturally-trained participants and

participants without architectural training has been used as criteria for selection of participants. Until now, however, all respondents shared an intellectual background. The effect of the home location on participants' environmental image has been tested in three different stances: in a first experiment, participants have all been selected as residents of the same town- Hasselt, in Belgium. The second test addressed participants who were residing in villages around the town of Hasselt, while in the last test participants were both residents of Hasselt and the surrounding villages.

With regard to the **technical** aspect, it was ascertain the necessity of using an all-in-one tool- a smart phone with a built-in GPS device-, running a location-based application which allow for easy shift between different annotation-modes. Everytrail application (www.everytrail.com) was selected to be employed in the first part of the game, since it performs very well as a mapping tool and also as a visualization platform. It allows for geotagged travel content to be uploaded, to create individual trip reports of people's experiences and also to correct one's input, by manually editing the content.

On a **conceptual** as well as on a **technical** level, the first tests of STEP I running as a social game, with players interacting with and grading each other, have pointed to various shortcomings of this concept. The inadequacy was confirmed by two facts. First, on a technical level, Everytrail platform proved its limitations, since it was not designed especially as a social tool, thus interaction between players was rather difficult. The most significant fact, however, was related to the conceptual level. Initially, interaction between the participants- and the grading- was introduced to trigger participants to find inspiration in other players' input. However this interaction performed differently than expected, creating a modification of priorities: the sharing activity, which was basically a consequence of visualizing the main activity of mapping, took priority over the mapping activity itself. In this way, players' attention shifted dramatically from mapping daily experiences, to other unintended concerns, such as impression management, annotations being selected in terms of their remarkable features, and their potential to impress others, when shared. Moreover no inspiration from the participants' input

was observed or confessed anyhow. At this point, players seemed to find more appealing the idea of presenting their own interpretations of the world (as a trophy) and sharing them with others, than to learn from others' experiences. In conclusion, it was decided for future experiments to introduce Step I as an ethnographic tool, which does not promote interaction between players, being given that the benefits of such interactions are insignificant for the purpose of the game- that of mapping participants' experiences.

On a **content** level, the discussion of the experiments with STEP I of the game can be structured around two focus areas: first, recordings of presence moments are identified and made explicit; next the concern shifts to identifying tensions and the tactics that people have developed from them.

At the outset, mapping of presence moments obviously involves a translation from presence into meaning, since these moments have been annotated through words. However, as Gumbrecht puts it, the focus falls on the quantity of these descriptions rather than on their quality, since the act of observing itself mostly matters, which ascertains the presence moments observation.

As illustrated by the annotations on location and the interviews that followed the monitoring-behavior week, moments of presence observation are extremely scarce. Most sensory perceptions asserted during STEP I have revealed the dominance of the visual stimuli in people's daily experiences. Interviews have shown that people with architectural training explain the choice of their annotations by relating to the physical structure of the environment ("I can see water, I see beautiful lights, and some kind of line: you see water, you see concrete, you see lights, you see trees, everything follows one line. And in summer is really beautiful there, because these trees are not the usual trees that grow up; they are some kind of shelf, protection for people" - Toerist), while participants without architectural training relate their choices mostly to the social aspect of their surroundings ("Don't we all love to watch people? (...) we all watch, I watch" - Majorie)

Only a minimum number of participants made conscious annotations of sensory perceptions which

involved other senses than the visual- more precisely, one participant (Saldek) and the researcher herself. It was noticed that these persons were previously trained to do so. In addition, Saldek proved to be the only respondent who read the instructions carefully enough to notice the request for annotating "places which have a sensory impact", and so he specially focused on his complete sensory experience (i.e. "smell of tandoori, or is it wok? definitely not incense", "the sound of party, the view of bikes").

The minor amount of annotations of this type proves that sensory perceptions related to other senses than the visual one are perceived mostly unconsciously and people do not pay attention to them unless they are specially asked for or if they become extremely intruding.

From here one can speculate that providing only the means (locative technology) to engage into presence observation is not enough. For further research it seems interesting to investigate how it would be possible to increase the number of such annotations, by imposing more focused guidance toward location-based challenges asking for conscious sensory experiences.

The next discussion will focus on the tensions which have been identified by observing participants behavior and through their testimonies in interviews and on the tactics that people develop for an enhanced coping with their surroundings.

In developing tactics people seem to employ the local knowledge acquired through the time of their residency in a specific place in order to act *effectively* in space and to create a *comfort zone* of action.

Respondents' movements during one week period, as well as their testimonies in interviews, illustrated that *efficiency* lies at the foundation of all human actions in the city. People constantly build and access their environmental image in terms of efficiency, given that most of the times movement is goal-directed, which implies a continuous interpretation of facts in light of one's own purpose.

"I usually try to combine walking and to buy something" (Toerist)

"If I go shopping to relax, I walk around, but if I go really quickly to get my shoes fixed or whatever,

then I am more functional and not really aware of what is happening." (Majorie)

Analysis of the collected data showed that every respondent holds his own pattern of needs and activities, regulated by his system of interpreting the world, developed progressively over a life time. For a particular individual, with specific sets of goals and values, his experience with the environment produces specific actions (Ittelson, 1978).

Through their actions, it was noticed how respondents try to achieve a maximum amount of *comfort*, which would provide a more relaxed coping with their surroundings (i.e. going only to certain areas of the city that "suits" one's status, during preferred times that would keep off traffic jams, according to preferred mode of transportation, creating an intimate space in crowded public spaces, etc). From here one can speculate that there is a natural aspiration for an existence that employs various tactics in an attempt to tackle tension. Depending on the experienced degree of contentment, participants' actions seek either to change or to maintain their relation with the environment. Such actions witness a progressive *adaptation* to the social, cultural and physical environment (i.e. adapting to an imposed dressing code policy, following natives' habits in order not to feel "foreigner") or, on the contrary, a need for *recognition* of one's own particularities as a different entity from the bulk (i.e. going only to some particular places, where certain type of people go, using the city in different ways than it was "prescribed", at unusual times, etc.). Both adaptation and recognition, however, produce tension. Adaptation entails a continuous internal concern with becoming an integral and accepted part of the society to which he considers himself part of, while recognition entails a double tension- that of being different from the majority, and, in parallel, that of integration in the particular group that one considers he belongs. So both approaches prove that tension is impossible to be eliminated, when living in society.

With regard to the different tensions produced among individuals and the imposed system of rules and regulations in urban space, an evocative example is that of the so-called "desire lines". Desire lines are paths developed as the result of

people's choice for efficiency, being the most convenient- shortest, easy navigable- routes; they are not developed through spatial experts' design, but from the erosion of users' footfall. In this respect, an interesting spatial intervention, characteristic for the town of Hasselt, are the bicycle and pedestrian roundabouts, situated at every big crossroads or bridge. They have been conceived to follow the same logic as the roundabouts for cars, but obviously they have never been used as such, since bikers and pedestrians find their way freely, unconstrained by so many spatial canons like cars do. The tension produced by this imposed spatial situation is perceived consciously by newcomers in town: "It seems nice, when you pass it, I mean, the trees, the circle, but it's not functional" (Toerist- one year resident), while long-term residents in Hasselt-who are also not using it as it was initially conceived- proved to have unconsciously adapted to this system: "I always take my own road. I don't look for indicated routes. I know you are either going left or right or straight, and then I don't watch the indications, I just follow the one I need. (..)Now this freedom gives you a lot of opportunity (..) I didn't even notice the fact that there was a... now as you said, I noticed that there was a direction that they tend to guide you into" (Mark). Tension, thus, can manifest consciously, generating a critical attitude materialized through complain or a "loud" desire for change, or it can manifest unconsciously, when people are adapting to the system, by creating their own functional solution to an imposed irrational rule. However, in order for the latter to occur, design must offer certain openness for the prospect of alternative solutions. Good design, thus, can support a diminution of tension, when it is conceived with consideration for individual tactics of functioning in the environment and for alternative uses. By virtue of this balance, future spatial proposals may be able to acknowledge and take into account the human factor and its interactions on all levels. In light of these observations, testing of the last phase of the game is now prepared to be launched in the very near future on the same groups of participants that have been testing STEP I.

CONCLUSIONS

While people continuously confer meaning to all their experiences in the physical and social environment, their environmental image is produced from an alteration of presence into meaning. In this way, each individual creates his personalized system of interpretation of the world, which produces tension, whenever is interacting with other individual or cultural systems of interpretation or with the substantial reality.

This paper aims to investigate if and how locative technologies employed in the first step of a ubiquitous urban game have the potential to tackle this tension, produced through an oscillation between presence effects and meaning effects, and if such approach may prove beneficial for the urban design practice.

Experiments with the first part of the game, employing locative technologies, made evident that people, unless prior trained, have lost their ability for conscious presence observation, achieved through complete sensory perception of their own bodies in space. In this respect, and as a future direction, the game may provide specialized training towards a reconnection with the substantial reality, training which can be materialized through location-based assignments.

In addition, experiments have shown that people possess a natural tendency to combat tension, by employing individualized tactics of coping with their living environment. Monitoring of daily experiences revealed how tension is manifested sometimes consciously, and most of the times unconsciously. Hence, for future research the game proposes a two-fold strategy, in order to bring presence and meaning in a satisfactory analogy, which would tackle the production of tension. First, a re-awakening of the desire for presence is intended -as the only tension-free state of existence-, by engaging people in consciously perceiving their surroundings. And then, Pask's Conversation Theory will be adopted as a methodology to facilitate a smoother distribution of knowledge between various (individual or cultural) systems of interpretation. This strategy is based on observation, rather than interpretation. Instead of performing actions based on the patterns developed through one's own system of interpretation, the game proposes sheer observation as the starting point of

any action. Grasping such a knowledge, produced through observation, may eventually result in a more self-aware and environmental-aware performance.

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